

VALIDATION OF A NOVEL MODEL FOR THE COMPRESSIVE RESPONSE OF FRP: NUMERICAL SIMULATION

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ABSTRACT

A progressive damage model for matrix compression is complemented with matrix tension in a physically based manner. The interaction of damage mechanisms undergoes a preliminary validation using single elements. The crushing response is validated with two different flat specimens with the fibres oriented transversely and at 45 degrees to the load. The model combines friction with damage to model the shear response accurately, which is necessary for reliable crush simulations. The behaviour in tension is history dependent, i.e. the model accounts for the stiffness reduction and strength to carry load in tension when previously damaged occurs in compression.

The validation is performed against different tests showing the reliability of the model for different fibre orientation, specimen geometry and multiaxial loading scenarios. The crush response is well captured as well as the geometry and location of the different damage mechanisms.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have found increasing application in many industries during the last decades. In the last few years the interest of the automotive industry stands out. Vehicles need to be lighter to satisfy the standards imposed by the regulation authorities based on environmental concerns. Composite cars can also take advantage of their excellent energy absorption during crash events [1,2]. To implement composites in the components of mainstream cars the following is required: more understanding of the response of composite components in vehicle crashes, a material database with relevant parameters, as well as enhanced predictive (crush) models to avoid expensive and time consuming testing and design iterations, [3], [4]. Crash is complex and not fully understood, neither modelled accurately. Some factors contributing to this complexity have been identified [5]: (i) the large strains and rotations involved; (ii) the interaction of complex damage mechanisms; (iii) significant geometric transformations in the crushing zone; (iv) material nonlinearity; (v) contact and friction and (vi) potential strain rate effects. The crash response will also depend on the geometry of the structure and the lay-up, which makes the energy-absorption not easily predicted, [6]. A predictive material model needs to account for all stages of all the mentioned phenomena, [7]. Most of the damage models for composite materials are based on the work of [8]. A damage variable is associated with a damage mode and degrades the stress associated with the respective failure mode.

The nonlinear behaviour of matrix compressive failure was identified by [9] using a Mohr-Coulomb criterion to include the effect of friction. The friction behaviour has been included in the failure initiation models by [10], [11]. Friction comes from the presence of microcracks in the composite, which greatly affect the failure envelope as demonstrated. However, after failure initiation, the microcracks increase in size and coalesce, implying even more important friction effects. Gutkin & Pinho [12] were the first authors to associate the residual stress to friction effects on damage progression of composite materials. Coupling damage with friction is important for the energy dissipation as well as to account for some of the nonlinear response in shear loading.

In this paper the Matrix Compression (MC) mode from [12] is modified and combined with Matrix Tension (MT) from [13] to allow both modes to occur simultaneously in the same element. The modifications introduced allow for a shear response calibrated with Iosipescu tests as shown in [14]. The fibre compression mode is also checked during the whole simulation using a maximum stress criterion. This check prevents unphysical stress values to occur during the crush simulation.

The present model behaves well for all the validation stages, such as mesh objectivity, shear response and crushing of simple structures such as flat specimens.

2. OVERVIEW OF THE MODEL

2.1. Constitutive relations

This model is based on the fixed crack model, i.e. the material constitutive law is defined on a potential fracture plane which is fixed when the failure initiation is reached and then remains fixed during the loading history, Figure 1. In the current implementation an exception is added when the MT damage mode is activated first (a fracture plane is fixed), followed by MC, where another fracture plane is allowed to occur.

Figure 1. Coordinate system (123) rotated to the fracture plane system (LNT)

The failure index is defined in the same way for both matrix tension and compression as

$$f_i = \max \left\{ \left(\frac{\tau_L}{S_L} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\tau_T}{S_T} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\langle \sigma_N \rangle}{Y_T} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha \in [0, \pi[$$

where, Y_T is the tensile strength and S_L and S_T are the shear strengths along and perpendicular to the fibres. The operator $\langle \cdot \rangle_+$ is the Mc-Cauley bracket defined by $\langle x \rangle = \max\{0, x\}$, meaning that the transverse term of the traction vanishes for normal compressive stresses. In this equation the friction effects typically present in compression [13] are not accounted for since the failure criterion refers to the beginning of nonlinearity and not to the peak load when the softening starts. The nonlinearity is partially due to formation of microcracks in the composite. Therefore, it becomes more physical to account for friction after the failure criterion is fulfilled.

The α in Eq. (1) is the trial fracture plane that varies between 0 and π and is fixed when the criterion has been fulfilled. In this fracture plane the stresses will be degraded in tension according to

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_N \\ \tau_L \\ \tau_T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} (1 - d_{mt} \langle \sigma_N \rangle_+ / \sigma_N) \tilde{\sigma}_N \\ (1 - d_{mt}) \tilde{\tau}_L \\ (1 - d_{mt}) \tilde{\tau}_T \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

and in compression

$$\begin{pmatrix} \sigma_N \\ \tau_L \\ \tau_T \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \tilde{\sigma}_N \\ (1 - d_{mc}) \tilde{\tau}_L \\ (1 - d_{mc}) \tilde{\tau}_T \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ d\tau_L^{friction} \\ d\tau_T^{friction} \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The friction only appears associated with the shear in the fracture plane and coupled with damage as in [12]. For tension the damage variables are defined as:

$$d_{mt} = 1 - \frac{\gamma_{o,mt}}{\gamma} \cdot \frac{\gamma_{f,mt} - \gamma}{\gamma_{f,mt} - \gamma_{o,mt}} \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma_{o,mt}$ is the strain at damage initiation and $\gamma_{f,mt}$ is based on the fracture toughness scaled to the element length according to [11]. The damage evolution in compression is given according to [15]

$$d_{mc} = \frac{\gamma^p - \gamma_{o,mc}^p}{\gamma_{f,mc}^p - \gamma_{o,mc}^p} \quad (5)$$

where $\gamma_{o,mc}$ and $\gamma_{f,mc}$ are the strains at initiation and full decohesion respectively. The exponent p is a calibration constant determined by [14].

2.2. Combining matrix tension and compression

The format of the current failure initiation criterion is the same in tension and compression. In contrast to some similar criteria for compressive failure (e.g. Puck and LaRC05) the friction component of the current model does not affect the failure index. Thus, the current failure index indicates the *onset* of nonlinearity, while the friction component is associated with the damage variable, which represents the development of the microcracks where friction is generated.

A common practice in Continuum-Damage Mechanics (CDM) is that each element represents a damage mode, i.e. once a damage mode is activated it is locked for the rest of the simulation. This can be a reasonable assumption when the stress state only changes slightly during the simulation. However, during crush simulations the stress state changes and load redistribution occurs, i.e. a compressive stress state will likely experience tensile stresses leading to parts (chunks) of the material falling out from the rest of the specimen. Defining failure initiation as the beginning of nonlinearities requires even more care since the damage mode will be defined earlier. Therefore, it is fundamental for reliable crush simulations to allow every material point to experience different damage modes simultaneously.

In the current model the effects of damage in matrix tension do not affect the behavior in matrix compression, representing thus the mechanism of cracks closure in compression. However, the damage created in compression will make the material very fragile in tension. These effects are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Loading unloading curves in the transverse direction

2.3. Material properties

The material data used in this manuscript were taken from [16], which provides further information about the characterization of the mechanical properties. The necessary parameters for the model were gathered in Table 1. S_L and S_T are the shear strengths in the material 1-3 and 2-3 planes, and μ_L and μ_T are the friction coefficients on the corresponding fracture planes. X_c is the peak stress during compression in the fibre direction. The parameter p_{0L} and p_{0T} accounts for the apparent internal pressure built up during manufacturing in longitudinal and transverse direction respectively. The shear modulus G_{23} is obtained assuming transverse isotropy since there is no shear test available to measure it. The out-of-plane tensile strength Z_t is assumed to be the same as the in-plane tensile strength Y_t since both values represent intralaminar failure. The shear strains at final rupture represent the moment when the specimen breaks and are used in the model. The final value for γ_{23} is not available experimentally. Therefore, one of two values was chosen inside the model according to dominant load being in-plane or out-of plane resulting in different transverse compression values, ($Z_c = 203$ and $Y_c = 129$).

Elastic properties				
Modulus (GPa)			Poisson's ratios	
$E_{11} = 136$	$E_{22} = 9.15$	$E_{33} = 7.7$	$\nu_{12} = 0.28$	$\nu_{32} = 0.43$
$G_{12} = 4.4$	$G_{23} = 3.02$	$G_{13} = 3.7$		
Strength properties (MPa)			Damage	
$X_c = 631$	$Y_c = 129$	$Z_t = Y_t = 29$	$p = -0.7$	$\gamma_f = 0.6$
$S_L = 78$	$S_T = 34$	$Z_c = 203$		
Friction properties				
Internal pressure (MPa)			Coefficient of friction	
$p_{0L} = 60$	$p_{0T} = 30$		$\mu_L = 0.34$	$\mu_T = 0.4$
Shear strain at final rupture (%)				
	$\gamma_{12} = 9.1$	$\gamma_{23} = 9.0/3.5$		

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the uni-weave NCF composite HTS45/LY556.

3. MODEL VALIDATION

3.1. Mesh objectivity and ply rupture

A cube with one element (1x1x1) was successively refined to a cube with 5x5x5 and tested in pure compression, Figure 3.

Figure 3: FE model response showing the mesh convergence, a) In-plane, b) Out-of-plane

The final rupture causes convergence difficulties due to the catastrophic softening behaviour as referred in [17]. The response of this abrupt rupture is not physically established and it is assumed to have low influence for crush. Therefore a new damage variable is defined with the aim of reducing the stress rapidly without causing instabilities. Once the final shear strains at rupture are reached the rapid decrease of stresses is represented by a second damage variable defined as

$$d_{mc}^{rupture} = 1 - (1 - d_{mc}^o) \cdot (1.02 - t/t_o) / 0.02 \quad (6)$$

where d_{mc}^o and t_o is the damage and the simulation time at the onset of ply rupture. The catastrophic failure progresses within 2% of t_o . This abrupt failure will cause instabilities if it was strain driven. Using the time to drive the strain is numerically stable and representative of an abrupt damage at the material point. This method avoids physical tests and also results in a mesh objective response, as the damage variable becomes dependent on the simulation time.

The shear strains when the Iosipescu specimen breaks are used in the material model, i.e. it is assumed that the breaking of the specimen occurs at the same strain levels as the breaking at the material point. By making this assumption it is no longer necessary to measure the intralaminar fracture toughness. The stress plateau is representative of a fully cracked ply in which only the friction acts between the fracture surfaces.

3.2. Shear behaviour

The shear deformation of Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRPs) is very nonlinear and inelastic. Since matrix compression is shear driven it is fundamental for reliable crush models to predict the shear response accurately. Complete unloading of a Iosipescu specimen at different load levels were performed experimentally to monitor the evolution of the permanent shear strains and the stiffness degradation. The experimental results for the average shear stress and strain in the gauge section are calibrated with the current model, Figure 4.

Figure 4: Response of the current damage model in pure in-plane shear versus experimental results

3.3. Flat crushing specimens

An explicit 3D stress analysis of flat crushing specimens was performed in ABAQUS 2016. The setup of the simulation is shown in Figure 5 together with the coarser and finer mesh used. Only half of the specimen (symmetry in the Z axis) was modeled to reduce the computational time. Fixed analytically rigid bodies are placed on the bottom and largest vertical sides of the specimen to simulate the constraints of the test rig. The friction coefficient between the specimen and the rigid bodies is 0.16. The loading was introduced by applying a vertical displacement smoothly increasing to 4.5 mm in the crushing plate located at the top of the specimen. Relatively small solid elements with reduced integration (C3D8R) were used with ABAQUS default hourglass control in order to capture the stress concentration during the crushing of the specimens. For simplicity, a linear elastic material and a bigger element size was used in the bottom of the specimens.

The numerical results are compared with the testing from [18] and a brief discussion on the damage mechanisms is carried out.

Element deletion is present in the model but not used for calibration. A scalar isotropic damage is activated when the shear strain reaches the value of 80%, degrading all stress components smoothly to zero. Element deletion occurs when the isotropic damage reaches the value one, meaning that all stress components are zero and element deletion has only visual effects without affecting the simulation.

Figure 5: Setup of the flat crushing specimens

3.4. Transverse crushing

The mechanisms present in crushing of transverse specimens are more complex than the failure in transverse compression. While transverse compression is dominated by shear stresses resulting in an inclined fracture plane, transverse crushing involves competing mechanisms changing during the load history.

The extension and morphology of the crushing zone is captured by the current model, Figure 6. Also, chunks of material start to disintegrate in the flat coupons and the same happens in the numerical simulation, causing the load drop observed. Differences in predicted and measured response appear to be related to rate and size of the disintegration, i.e. fewer and larger chunks in the FE model and many smaller crumbs in the experiment.

Figure 6: Model validation using flat coupon specimens with fibres oriented at 90°: (Top) Matrix compressive damage of the specimens during crushing; (Bottom) FE response correlated with the experiments

3.5. Crushing at 45 degrees with fibres

The mechanisms present in the crushing of 45° off-axis specimens are well predicted by the model, Figure 7. This type of crushing seems to be mainly shear driven with the formation of inclined microcracks following the orientation of the fibres, as shown in Figure 7 (Top).

Figure 7: Model validation using flat coupon specimens with fibres oriented at $\sim 45^\circ$: (Top) Matrix compressive damage of the specimens during crushing; (Bottom) FE response correlated with the experiments

4. CONCLUSIONS

Modelling the nonlinear shear response accurately allows very reliable crush simulations when the shear behaviour is the main mechanism present during the crush, such as in the 45° off-axis specimen. Having a mesh objective shear response and accounting for the interaction of damage modes in the same material point is essential for accurate modelling of crushing, especially in the transverse specimen. Using the shear strains when the Iosipescu specimen fails as the strain at rupture eliminates the need for the measurement of transverse intralaminar toughness.

The results show that element deletion is almost nonexistent for all simulations thus avoiding undesired unphysical effects. Mesh dependency, a typical problem in crash simulations, seems to have low influence in the crush response showing the robustness of the model for different meshes.

Some orthotropic effects are included in the model which allows distinguishing between in-plane and out-of-plane transverse compression. The shear behaviour 1-2, 1-3 and 2-3 also presents some differentiation but is not fully representative of the experiments. This will be investigated further.

The competition of matrix tension and matrix compression govern the damage behavior in the Iosipescu specimen, which will be presented in a subsequent journal paper.

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